

1 **Sod1 mutation results in cycling defects in a paradigm for etiology of chronic disease.**

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7 We used Sod1 as a model to describe the early events in genesis of a chronic human disease. The
8 immediate phenotypic consequences of mutant expression triggered cellular dysfunction most specifically
9 in lysosomal biogenesis and nutrient sensing, vesicle trafficking and secretory pathway (Er to Golgi)
10 function but affected cellular function across systems. We describe a cell or tissue specific requirement for
11 shift at least two additional and separate factors in driving the homeostatic collapse that is a requirement
12 for entry into disease: redox status involving thioredoxins and isomerase functions associated with protein
13 folding, a general requirement we observed in disease settings not caused by a gene with catalytic
14 function in redox chemistry. The change in cell cycle activity that leads to oncogene activation, and
15 acquisition of a novel cellular identity (expression of a combinatorial code of nuclear factor) is based on
16 cellular dysfunction caused by the disease. The expression level of the gene, dictated by its
17 developmental and tissue specific expression patterns, and the nature of the variant, which shape the
18 cellular phenotype following variant repression, dictate cell of origin and disease behavior.
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